

miRNA: Introduction, Profiling Methods, and Applications

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are a class of non-coding RNAs of approximately 20-24 nucleotides in length. By base-pairing to the targeted mRNA, miRNA promotes mRNA degradation or represses its translation and participates in the post-transcriptional regulation, thereby inhibiting targeted gene expression. miRNAs are involved in various biological processes such as cell proliferation, apoptosis, differentiation, metabolism, and development and can function as biomarkers or disease regulators.

miRNA Profiling Methods

miRNA Sequencing

Deep sequencing enables a comprehensive, in-depth, and detailed analysis of genome or transcriptome of the organism, tissue, or even cell and organelle. Through deep sequencing technology, we can explore and discover unknown miRNAs as well as perform preliminary qualitative and semi-quantitative analyses of known miRNAs.

Gene microarray is a rapid and high-throughput technology for measuring gene expression through the principle of nucleic acid hybridization. One of the highlights of this technology applied to miRNA research involves its extremely high detection throughput and low detection cost. However, the microarray is a qualitative and semi-quantitative detection technology.

miRNA Microarray

Why do we study miRNAs?

1. They are important icebreakers for exosome research

Exosomes contain a variety of different molecules, among which miRNAs have attracted the most attention due to their important roles in the regulation of gene expression. Scientists have found that of all small RNAs, miRNAs reveal a higher proportion in exosomes than in cells of their origins. Although exosomes contain several hundred miRNAs, miRNAs are not randomly integrated into exosomes. Through exosomal miRNA sequencing, researchers can obtain disease-related biomarkers so as to discover effective drug targets through liquid biopsy in the field of tumor treatment in the future.

2. They can be used as biomarkers

First, miRNAs have various compositions in different tissues, cells, and developmental stages of cells; Secondly, miRNAs are very stable and can endure repeated freezing and thawing, pH changes, DNA and RNA cleavage enzymes. In addition, only a few miRNAs can regulate multiple expressions, which also determines that the number of miRNAs will not be extensively present. Recent studies indicate that the total number of miRNAs found in the human body is 1048. Therefore, miRNA has the characteristics of being high-quality biomarkers.

3. They can work as potential drug targets

miRNAs are involved in biological processes by regulating a group of proteins with similar functions; thus, blockage of miRNAs to regulate physiological functions would be safe strategies for organisms theoretically. Therefore, miRNAs are potential drug targets.

4. They are fundamental research subjects

Through the study of miRNA, proteins can be reclassified according to their functions. As a result, proteins that reveal novel functions can be predicted and linked with new signaling pathways to expand the horizons of basic scientific research.

The broad prospects of miRNA research

Researchers can monitor changes in the expression of a large number of known miRNAs in the immune response to discover the important roles in the physiological and pathological states. In addition, researchers can also learn and identify new biomarkers to monitor the signal transduction of immune cells and the differentiation of tissues and organs.

Novel research finds that miRNAs play a role in the directional differentiation and self-renewal function maintenance of stem cells. Thus, researchers can quickly discover new stem cell differentiation markers using miRNAs. In addition, by detecting the expression of known miRNA markers, we can monitor the pluripotency and differentiation of stem cells.

Certain miRNAs play important roles in the occurrence and development of tumors. According to the special role of miRNAs in regulating protein production in the human body, it is believed that miRNAs have broad prospects in future clinical detection applications.

The use of the latest high-throughput technologies such as miRNA microarray and miRNA-Seq allows further in-depth research on the mechanism of miRNA functions. CD Genomics excels in providing a comprehensive portfolio of sequencing services. Our miRNA-Seq and miRNA microarray will help you study the role of miRNAs in cell differentiation, biological development, disease development, and beyond.